

FOUR AND FIVE FIGURES OF KIFILIDEEN (POWER OF BASE 11) AND ANTIKIFILIDEEN (ANTIPOWER OF BASE 11) TABLES

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Abstract

The four figures of power of base numbers tables is need to be created for easy synchronization with existing Logarithm table of power of base 10 which is working on four figures. Although the five figures of power of base numbers tables is more accurate because it is having less approximation in its establishment. The four figure tables is easy to compute doing utilization because it is having less digit to work with. This paper presents the four and five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables for the computation of mathematical problem. The four and five figures are both reliable to work with. However there is tradeoff between easy computation (as related to four figure table) and more accuracy (as related to five figure table) in their utilization.

Keywords: Kifilideen Table, AntiKifilideen Table, Four Figure, Five Figure, FUNAAB, Power of base 11

INTRODUCTION

The four figure of power of base numbers tables is need to be created for easy synchronization with existing Logarithm table of power of base 10 which is working on four figures. Although the five figure of power of base numbers tables is more accurate because it is having less approximation in its establishment. The four figure tables is easy to compute doing utilization because it is having less digit to work with. This paper presents the four and five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables for the computation of mathematical problem.

METHODOLOGY IN THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE FOUR FIGURES OF KIFILIDEEN (POWER OF BASE 11) TABLE

Tables 1-4 present the establishment of four figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables while Tables 4-8 indicate the five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables. The Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables were inaugurated based on manual method of computing and also with the assistance of calculator (Osanyinpeju et al., 2019). However, the tables can be used to solve modern real life problem without the use of calculator. The genesis of the manual method used to construct these tables mentioned above is demonstrated as follows: To convert 44 to the power of base 11, you start by looking for the value to be raised by 11 to give 44. $11^1 = 11$ which is less than the 44 to be achieved. Then, the power of the base 11 is increased. So, we try 11^2 which gives 121. The value obtained is greater than the value we needed that is 44. Then, the power is reduced to 1.5. Meanwhile, $11^{1.5} = 36.4829$. This value attained is getting closer to the required value. So, $11^{1.57}$ is tried which gives 43.1506 but $3^{1.58}$ gives 44.1978. The power is then given a 3 decimal places trial. For $3^{1.578}$ we have 43.9863 but $3^{1.579}$ produces 44.0919. With this power 1.578 we are almost there. We go for power of 4 decimal places. Trying $3^{1.5781}$ we obtained 33.9969. Trying $3^{1.5782}$ we obtained 34.0074. For 5 decimal places, $3^{1.57813}$ gives 44.0000. Since the table was constructed base on power of 4 and 5 decimal places. So the four figures power in which 11 must be raised to give 44 is 1.5781 indicating $Kif(44)$ is 1.5781 or $44 = 11^{Kif(44)} = 11^{1.5781}$. So the five figures power in which 11 must be raised to give 44 is 1.57813 indicating $Kif(44)$ is 1.57813 or $44 = 11^{Kif(44)} = 11^{1.57813}$. The five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables had been in existing and was first published in 2019 (Osanyinpeju, 2019; Osanyinpeju, 2020).

Table 1: Kifilideen (Power of base 11) of Number in Four Figure

$x \rightarrow Kif\ x$

(x)											Difference								
	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	0.0000	0.0397	0.0760	0.1094	0.1403	0.1691	0.1960	0.2213	0.2451	0.2677	30	60	89	118	147	176	205	233	261
2	0.2891	0.3094	0.3288	0.3474	0.3651	0.3821	0.3985	0.4142	0.4294	0.4440	17	34	51	68	85	102	119	136	152
3	0.4582	0.4718	0.4851	0.4979	0.5104	0.5224	0.5342	0.5456	0.5567	0.5676	12	24	36	48	60	72	86	96	108
4	0.5781	0.5884	0.5985	0.6083	0.6179	0.6272	0.6364	0.6454	0.6542	0.6628	9	19	28	37	47	56	65	75	84
5	0.6712	0.6794	0.6875	0.6955	0.7033	0.7109	0.7184	0.7258	0.7331	0.7402	8	15	23	31	38	46	53	61	68
6	0.7472	0.7541	0.7609	0.7676	0.7741	0.7806	0.7870	0.7932	0.7994	0.8055	6	13	19	26	32	39	45	52	58
7	0.8115	0.8174	0.8233	0.8290	0.8347	0.8403	0.8458	0.8513	0.8566	0.8619	6	11	17	22	28	34	39	45	50
8	0.8672	0.8724	0.8775	0.8825	0.8875	0.8925	0.8974	0.9022	0.9069	0.9117	5	10	15	20	25	30	34	39	44
9	0.9163	0.9209	0.9255	0.9300	0.9344	0.9389	0.9432	0.9476	0.9518	0.9561	4	9	13	18	22	26	31	35	40
10	0.9603	0.9644	0.9685	0.9726	0.9766	0.9806	0.9846	0.9885	0.9923	0.9962	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36
11	1.0000	1.0038	1.0075	1.0112	1.0149	1.0185	1.0221	1.0257	1.0293	1.0328	4	7	11	15	18	22	25	29	33
12	1.0363	1.0397	1.0432	1.0466	1.0500	1.0533	1.0566	1.0599	1.0632	1.0664	3	7	10	13	17	20	23	27	30
13	1.0697	1.0729	1.0760	1.0792	1.0823	1.0854	1.0885	1.0915	1.0946	1.0976	3	6	9	12	15	19	22	25	28
14	1.1006	1.1035	1.1065	1.1094	1.1123	1.1152	1.1181	1.1209	1.1237	1.1266	3	6	9	12	14	17	20	23	26
15	1.1293	1.1321	1.1349	1.1376	1.1403	1.1430	1.1457	1.1484	1.1510	1.1536	3	5	8	11	13	16	19	22	24
16	1.1563	1.1589	1.1614	1.1640	1.1666	1.1691	1.1716	1.1741	1.1766	1.1791	3	5	8	10	13	15	18	20	23
17	1.1815	1.1840	1.1864	1.1888	1.1912	1.1936	1.1960	1.1984	1.2007	1.2031	2	5	7	10	12	14	17	19	21
18	1.2054	1.2077	1.2100	1.2123	1.2145	1.2168	1.2191	1.2213	1.2235	1.2257	2	5	7	9	11	14	16	18	20
19	1.2279	1.2301	1.2323	1.2345	1.2366	1.2388	1.2409	1.2430	1.2451	1.2472	2	4	6	9	11	13	15	17	19
20	1.2493	1.2514	1.2535	1.2555	1.2576	1.2596	1.2616	1.2637	1.2657	1.2677	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18
21	1.2697	1.2716	1.2736	1.2756	1.2775	1.2795	1.2814	1.2833	1.2853	1.2872	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	17
22	1.2891	1.2910	1.2928	1.2947	1.2966	1.2984	1.3003	1.3021	1.3040	1.3058	2	4	6	7	9	11	13	15	17
23	1.3076	1.3094	1.3112	1.3130	1.3148	1.3166	1.3183	1.3201	1.3219	1.3236	2	4	5	7	9	11	12	14	16
24	1.3254	1.3271	1.3288	1.3305	1.3322	1.3340	1.3356	1.3373	1.3390	1.3407	2	3	5	7	9	10	12	14	15
25	1.3424	1.3440	1.3457	1.3474	1.3490	1.3506	1.3523	1.3539	1.3555	1.3571	2	3	5	7	8	10	11	13	15
26	1.3587	1.3603	1.3619	1.3635	1.3651	1.3667	1.3682	1.3698	1.3714	1.3729	2	3	5	6	8	9	11	13	14
27	1.3745	1.3760	1.3775	1.3791	1.3806	1.3821	1.3836	1.3851	1.3866	1.3881	2	3	5	6	8	9	11	12	14
28	1.3896	1.3911	1.3926	1.3941	1.3956	1.3970	1.3985	1.3999	1.4014	1.4028	1	3	4	6	7	9	10	12	13
29	1.4043	1.4057	1.4071	1.4086	1.4100	1.4114	1.4128	1.4142	1.4156	1.4170	1	3	4	6	7	8	10	11	13
30	1.4184	1.4198	1.4212	1.4226	1.4239	1.4253	1.4267	1.4280	1.4294	1.4307	1	3	4	5	7	8	10	11	12
31	1.4321	1.4334	1.4348	1.4361	1.4374	1.4388	1.4401	1.4414	1.4427	1.4440	1	3	4	5	7	8	9	11	12
32	1.4453	1.4466	1.4479	1.4492	1.4505	1.4518	1.4531	1.4543	1.4556	1.4569	1	3	4	5	6	8	9	10	12
33	1.4582	1.4594	1.4607	1.4619	1.4632	1.4644	1.4657	1.4669	1.4681	1.4694	1	2	4	5	6	7	9	10	11
34	1.4706	1.4718	1.4731	1.4743	1.4755	1.4767	1.4779	1.4791	1.4803	1.4815	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	10	11
35	1.4827	1.4839	1.4851	1.4863	1.4874	1.4886	1.4898	1.4910	1.4921	1.4933	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	11
36	1.4944	1.4956	1.4968	1.4979	1.4991	1.5002	1.5013	1.5025	1.5036	1.5047	1	2	3	5	6	7	8	9	10
37	1.5059	1.5070	1.5081	1.5092	1.5104	1.5115	1.5126	1.5137	1.5148	1.5159	1	2	3	4	6	7	8	9	10
38	1.5170	1.5181	1.5192	1.5203	1.5214	1.5224	1.5235	1.5246	1.5257	1.5268	1	2	3	4	5	7	8	9	10
39	1.5278	1.5289	1.5300	1.5310	1.5321	1.5331	1.5342	1.5352	1.5363	1.5373	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	10
40	1.5384	1.5394	1.5405	1.5415	1.5425	1.5436	1.5446	1.5456	1.5466	1.5477	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
41	1.5487	1.5497	1.5507	1.5517	1.5527	1.5537	1.5547	1.5557	1.5567	1.5577	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
42	1.5587	1.5597	1.5607	1.5617	1.5627	1.5637	1.5646	1.5656	1.5666	1.5676	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
43	1.5685	1.5695	1.5705	1.5714	1.5724	1.5734	1.5743	1.5753	1.5762	1.5772	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
44	1.5781	1.5791	1.5800	1.5810	1.5819	1.5828	1.5838	1.5847	1.5856	1.5866	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	7	8
45	1.5875	1.5884	1.5894	1.5903	1.5912	1.5921	1.5930	1.5939	1.5949	1.5958	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	7	8
46	1.5967	1.5976	1.5985	1.5994	1.6003	1.6012	1.6021	1.6030	1.6039	1.6047	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	7	8
47	1.6056	1.6065	1.6074	1.6083	1.6092	1.6100	1.6109	1.6118	1.6127	1.6135	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	7	8
48	1.6144	1.6153	1.6162	1.6170	1.6179	1.6187	1.6196	1.6205	1.6213	1.6222	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8
49	1.6230	1.6239	1.6247	1.6256	1.6264	1.6272	1.6281	1.6289	1.6298	1.6306	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8
50	1.6314	1.6323	1.6331	1.6339	1.6348	1.6356	1.6364	1.6372	1.6381	1.6389	1	2	2	3	4	5	6	7	7
51	1.6397	1.6405	1.6413	1.6421	1.6430	1.6438	1.6446	1.6454	1.6462	1.6470	1	2	2	3	4	5	6	6	7
52	1.6478	1.6486	1.6494	1.6502	1.6510	1.6518	1.6526	1.6534	1.6542	1.6550	1	2	2	3	4	5	6	6	7
53	1.6557	1.6565	1.6573	1.6581	1.6589	1.6597	1.6604	1.6612	1.6620	1.6628	1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6	7
54	1.6635	1.6643	1.6651	1.6658	1.6666	1.6674	1.6681	1.6689	1.6697	1.6704	1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6	7
55	1.6712	1.6719	1.6727	1.6735	1.6742	1.6750	1.6757	1.6765	1.6772	1.6780	1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6	7
56	1.6787	1.6794	1.6802	1.6809	1.6817	1.6824	1.6831	1.6839	1.6846	1.6854	1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	7
57	1.6861	1.6868	1.6875	1.6883	1.6890	1.6897	1.6905	1.6912	1.6919	1.6926	1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	7
58	1.6933	1.6941	1.6948	1.6955	1.6962	1.6969	1.6976	1.6983	1.6990	1.6998	1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	6
59	1.7005	1.7012	1.7019	1.7026	1.7033	1.7040	1.7047	1.7054	1.7061	1.7068	1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	6
60	1.7075	1.7082	1.7089	1.7096	1.7102	1.7109	1.7116	1.7123	1.7130	1.7137	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	6
61	1.7144	1.7151	1.7157	1.7164	1.7171	1.7178	1.7184	1.7191	1.7198	1.7205	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
62	1.7211	1.7218	1.7225	1.7232	1.7238	1.7245	1.7252	1.7258	1.7265	1.7272	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
63	1.7278	1.7285	1.7291	1.7298	1.7305	1.7311	1.7318	1.7324	1.7331	1.7337	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
64	1.7344	1.7350	1.7357	1.7363	1.7370	1.7376	1.7383	1.7389	1.7396	1.7402	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
65	1.7409	1.7415	1.7421	1.7428	1.7434	1.7441	1.7447	1.7453	1.7460	1.7466	1	1	2	3	3	4	4	5	6
66	1.7472	1.7479	1.7485	1.7491	1.7497	1.7504	1.7510	1.7516	1.7522	1.7529	1	1	2	3	3	4	4	5	6
67	1.7535	1.7541	1.7547	1.7554	1.7560	1.7566	1.7572	1.7578	1.7584	1.7591	1	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	6
68	1.7597	1.7603	1.7609	1.7615	1.7621	1.7													

73	1.7893	1.7898	1.7904	1.7910	1.7915	1.7921	1.7927	1.7932	1.7938	1.7944		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	5	5
74	1.7949	1.7955	1.7961	1.7966	1.7972	1.7977	1.7983	1.7989	1.7994	1.8000		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
75	1.8005	1.8011	1.8016	1.8022	1.8028	1.8033	1.8039	1.8044	1.8050	1.8055		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
76	1.8061	1.8066	1.8072	1.8077	1.8082	1.8088	1.8093	1.8099	1.8104	1.8110		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
77	1.8115	1.8120	1.8126	1.8131	1.8137	1.8142	1.8147	1.8153	1.8158	1.8164		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
78	1.8169	1.8174	1.8180	1.8185	1.8190	1.8196	1.8201	1.8206	1.8211	1.8217		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
79	1.8222	1.8227	1.8233	1.8238	1.8243	1.8248	1.8254	1.8259	1.8264	1.8269		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
80	1.8274	1.8280	1.8285	1.8290	1.8295	1.8300	1.8306	1.8311	1.8316	1.8321		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
81	1.8326	1.8331	1.8337	1.8342	1.8347	1.8352	1.8357	1.8362	1.8367	1.8372		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
82	1.8377	1.8383	1.8388	1.8393	1.8398	1.8403	1.8408	1.8413	1.8418	1.8423		1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5
83	1.8428	1.8433	1.8438	1.8443	1.8448	1.8453	1.8458	1.8463	1.8468	1.8473		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
84	1.8478	1.8483	1.8488	1.8493	1.8498	1.8503	1.8508	1.8513	1.8517	1.8522		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
85	1.8527	1.8532	1.8537	1.8542	1.8547	1.8552	1.8557	1.8561	1.8566	1.8571		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
86	1.8576	1.8581	1.8586	1.8591	1.8595	1.8600	1.8605	1.8610	1.8615	1.8619		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
87	1.8624	1.8629	1.8634	1.8639	1.8643	1.8648	1.8653	1.8658	1.8662	1.8667		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
88	1.8672	1.8677	1.8681	1.8686	1.8691	1.8696	1.8700	1.8705	1.8710	1.8714		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
89	1.8719	1.8724	1.8728	1.8733	1.8738	1.8742	1.8747	1.8752	1.8756	1.8761		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
90	1.8766	1.8770	1.8775	1.8780	1.8784	1.8789	1.8793	1.8798	1.8803	1.8807		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
91	1.8812	1.8816	1.8821	1.8825	1.8830	1.8835	1.8839	1.8844	1.8848	1.8853		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
92	1.8857	1.8862	1.8866	1.8871	1.8875	1.8880	1.8884	1.8889	1.8893	1.8898		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
93	1.8902	1.8907	1.8911	1.8916	1.8920	1.8925	1.8929	1.8934	1.8938	1.8943		0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
94	1.8947	1.8951	1.8956	1.8960	1.8965	1.8969	1.8974	1.8978	1.8982	1.8987		0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
95	1.8991	1.8996	1.9000	1.9004	1.9009	1.9013	1.9017	1.9022	1.9026	1.9030		0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
96	1.9035	1.9039	1.9043	1.9048	1.9052	1.9056	1.9061	1.9065	1.9069	1.9074		0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
97	1.9078	1.9082	1.9087	1.9091	1.9095	1.9099	1.9104	1.9108	1.9112	1.9117		0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
98	1.9121	1.9125	1.9129	1.9134	1.9138	1.9142	1.9146	1.9150	1.9155	1.9159		0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4
99	1.9163	1.9167	1.9172	1.9176	1.9180	1.9184	1.9188	1.9193	1.9197	1.9201		0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4

Table 2: Kifilideen (Power of base 11) of 10ⁿ in Four Figures

Kif(10ⁿ)

10 ⁿ	11 ¹												
	Kif(10 ⁿ)												
1	0.9603	16	15.364	31	29.7678	46	44.1716	61	58.5754	76	72.9792	91	87.3830
2	1.9205	17	16.3243	32	30.7281	47	45.1319	62	59.5357	77	73.9394	92	88.3432
3	2.8808	18	17.2845	33	31.6883	48	46.0921	63	60.4959	78	74.8997	93	89.3035
4	3.8410	19	18.2448	34	32.6486	49	47.0524	64	61.4562	79	75.8600	94	90.2637
5	4.8013	20	19.2051	35	33.6088	50	48.0126	65	62.4164	80	76.8202	95	91.2240
6	5.7615	21	20.1653	36	34.5691	51	48.9729	66	63.3767	81	77.7805	96	92.1842
7	6.7218	22	21.1256	37	35.5293	52	49.9331	67	64.3369	82	78.7407	97	93.1445
8	7.6820	23	22.0858	38	36.4896	53	50.8934	68	65.2972	83	79.7010	98	94.1048
9	8.6423	24	23.0461	39	37.4499	54	51.8536	69	66.2574	84	80.6612	99	95.0650
10	9.6025	25	24.0063	40	38.4101	55	52.8139	70	67.2177	85	81.6215		
11	10.5628	26	24.9666	41	39.3704	56	53.7741	71	68.1779	86	82.5817		
12	11.5230	27	25.9268	42	40.3306	57	54.7344	72	69.1382	87	83.5420		
13	12.4833	28	26.8871	43	41.2909	58	55.6946	73	70.0984	88	84.5022		
14	13.4435	29	27.8473	44	42.2511	59	56.6549	74	71.0587	89	85.4625		
15	14.4038	30	28.8076	45	43.2114	60	57.6152	75	72.0189	90	86.4227		

Table 3: AntiKifilideen (AntiPower of base 11) of Number in Four Figures

x → AntiKif x

(x)	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.007	0.008	0.009	Difference									
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
0.00	1.0000	1.0024	1.0048	1.0072	1.0096	1.0121	1.0145	1.0169	1.0194	1.0218	2	5	7	0	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.01	1.0243	1.0267	1.0292	1.0317	1.0341	1.0366	1.0391	1.0416	1.0441	1.0466	2	5	7	0	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.02	1.0491	1.0516	1.0542	1.0567	1.0592	1.0618	1.0643	1.0669	1.0694	1.0720	3	5	8	0	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.03	1.0746	1.0772	1.0798	1.0823	1.0849	1.0875	1.0902	1.0928	1.0954	1.0980	3	5	8	0	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.04	1.1007	1.1033	1.1060	1.1086	1.1113	1.1139	1.1166	1.1193	1.1220	1.1247	3	5	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.05	1.1274	1.1301	1.1328	1.1355	1.1382	1.1410	1.1437	1.1465	1.1492	1.1520	3	5	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.06	1.1547	1.1575	1.1603	1.1631	1.1659	1.1687	1.1715	1.1743	1.1771	1.1799	3	6	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.07	1.1828	1.1856	1.1884	1.1913	1.1942	1.1970	1.1999	1.2028	1.2057	1.2086	3	6	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.08	1.2115	1.2144	1.2173	1.2202	1.2231	1.2261	1.2290	1.2320	1.2349	1.2379	3	6	9	2	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.09	1.2409	1.2438	1.2468	1.2498	1.2528	1.2558	1.2588	1.2619	1.2649	1.2679	3	6	9	2	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.10	1.2710	1.2740	1.2771	1.2802	1.2832	1.2863	1.2894	1.2925	1.2956	1.2987	3	6	9	2	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.11	1.3018	1.3050	1.3081	1.3112	1.3144	1.3175	1.3207	1.3239	1.3270	1.3302	3	6	9	3	1	1	1	1	1	2
0.12	1.3334	1.3366	1.3398	1.3430	1.3463	1.3495	1.3527	1.3560	1.3592	1.3625	3	6	0	3	6	9	3	6	9	3
0.13	1.3658	1.3691	1.3723	1.3756	1.3789	1.3823	1.3856	1.3889	1.3922	1.3956	3	7	0	3	7	0	3	7	0	3
0.14	1.3989	1.4023	1.4057	1.4090	1.4124	1.4158	1.4192	1.4226	1.4260	1.4294	3	7	0	4	7	0	4	7	0	3
0.15	1.4329	1.4363	1.4398	1.4432	1.4467	1.4502	1.4536	1.4571	1.4606	1.4641	3	7	0	4	7	1	1	1	1	2
0.16	1.4677	1.4712	1.4747	1.4782	1.4818	1.4854	1.4889	1.4925	1.4961	1.4997	4	7	1	1	4	8	1	5	8	2
0.17	1.5033	1.5069	1.5105	1.5141	1.5178	1.5214	1.5251	1.5287	1.5324	1.5361	4	7	1	1	5	8	2	6	9	3
0.18	1.5398	1.5434	1.5472	1.5509	1.5546	1.5583	1.5621	1.5658	1.5696	1.5733	4	7	1	1	5	9	2	6	0	4
0.19	1.5771	1.5809	1.5847	1.5885	1.5923	1.5961	1.6000	1.6038	1.6077	1.6115	4	8	1	1	5	9	3	7	1	4

0.70	5.3577	5.3705	5.3834	5.3963	5.4093	5.4223	5.4353	5.4483	5.4614	5.4745	1 3	2 6	3 9	5 2	6 5	7 8	9 1	1 4	1 7
0.71	5.4877	5.5009	5.5141	5.5273	5.5406	5.5539	5.5672	5.5806	5.5940	5.6074	1 3	2 7	4 0	5 3	6 7	8 0	9 3	1 7	1 0
0.72	5.6209	5.6344	5.6479	5.6614	5.6750	5.6887	5.7023	5.716	5.7297	5.7435	1 4	2 7	4 1	5 5	6 8	8 2	9 5	1 9	1 2
0.73	5.7573	5.7711	5.7849	5.7988	5.8128	5.8267	5.8407	5.8547	5.8688	5.8829	1 4	2 8	4 1	5 5	6 8	8 2	9 5	1 9	1 2
0.74	5.8970	5.9111	5.9253	5.9396	5.9538	5.9681	5.9824	5.9968	6.0112	6.0256	1 4	2 9	4 3	5 7	6 2	8 6	9 0	1 4	1 9
0.75	6.0401	6.0546	6.0691	6.0837	6.0983	6.1130	6.1276	6.1423	6.1571	6.1719	1 5	2 9	4 4	5 8	6 3	8 7	9 1	1 5	1 3
0.76	6.1867	6.2015	6.2164	6.2314	6.2463	6.2613	6.2763	6.2914	6.3065	6.3217	1 5	3 0	4 5	6 0	7 5	9 0	1 5	1 0	1 3
0.77	6.3368	6.3520	6.3673	6.3826	6.3979	6.4133	6.4287	6.4441	6.4596	6.4751	1 5	3 1	4 6	6 7	7 9	9 2	1 6	1 2	1 3
0.78	6.4906	6.5062	6.5218	6.5375	6.5532	6.5689	6.5847	6.6005	6.6163	6.6322	1 6	3 1	4 7	6 3	7 9	9 4	1 0	1 6	1 4
0.79	6.6481	6.6641	6.6801	6.6961	6.7122	6.7283	6.7445	6.7607	6.7769	6.7932	1 6	3 2	4 8	6 4	7 9	9 3	1 7	1 3	1 5
0.80	6.8095	6.8258	6.8422	6.8586	6.8751	6.8916	6.9082	6.9247	6.9414	6.9580	1 7	3 3	5 0	6 6	8 3	9 6	1 0	1 3	1 4
0.81	6.9747	6.9915	7.0083	7.0251	7.0420	7.0589	7.0758	7.0928	7.1098	7.1269	1 7	3 4	5 1	6 8	8 5	9 2	1 6	1 3	1 5
0.82	7.1440	7.1612	7.1784	7.1956	7.2129	7.2302	7.2475	7.2649	7.2824	7.2999	1 7	3 5	5 2	6 9	8 7	9 4	1 7	1 4	1 6
0.83	7.3174	7.3350	7.3526	7.3702	7.3879	7.4056	7.4234	7.4412	7.4591	7.4770	1 8	3 5	5 3	7 1	8 9	9 6	1 7	1 4	1 6
0.84	7.4950	7.5130	7.5310	7.5491	7.5672	7.5854	7.6036	7.6218	7.6401	7.6585	1 8	3 6	5 5	7 3	9 0	1 9	1 7	1 4	1 6
0.85	7.6769	7.6953	7.7138	7.7323	7.7509	7.7695	7.7881	7.8068	7.8256	7.8443	1 9	3 7	5 6	7 4	9 3	1 2	1 8	1 5	1 7
0.86	7.8632	7.8820	7.9010	7.9199	7.9390	7.9580	7.9771	7.9963	8.0155	8.0347	1 9	3 8	5 7	7 6	9 5	1 4	1 3	1 5	1 7
0.87	8.0540	8.0733	8.0927	8.1121	8.1316	8.1511	8.1707	8.1903	8.2100	8.2297	2 0	3 9	5 9	7 8	9 8	1 7	1 3	1 5	1 7
0.88	8.2495	8.2693	8.2891	8.3090	8.3290	8.3490	8.3690	8.3891	8.4092	8.4294	2 0	4 0	6 0	8 0	0 0	2 4	2 0	4 6	8 0
0.89	8.4497	8.4700	8.4903	8.5107	8.5311	8.5516	8.5721	8.5927	8.6133	8.6340	2 0	4 1	6 1	8 2	1 2	2 3	3 4	5 6	8 8
0.90	8.6547	8.6755	8.6963	8.7172	8.7381	8.7591	8.7801	8.8012	8.8224	8.8435	2 1	4 2	6 3	8 4	0 5	2 6	4 7	6 8	8 9
0.91	8.8648	8.8860	8.9074	8.9288	8.9502	8.9717	8.9932	9.0148	9.0365	9.0582	2 1	4 3	6 4	8 6	1 9	1 0	2 1	4 2	6 4
0.92	9.0799	9.1017	9.1236	9.1455	9.1674	9.1894	9.2115	9.2336	9.2558	9.2780	2 2	4 4	6 6	8 8	1 3	2 5	4 6	6 8	9 9
0.93	9.3003	9.3226	9.3450	9.3674	9.3899	9.4124	9.4350	9.4577	9.4804	9.5032	2 3	4 5	6 8	9 0	1 3	2 5	4 8	6 1	8 3
0.94	9.5260	9.5488	9.5718	9.5947	9.6178	9.6409	9.6640	9.6872	9.7105	9.7338	2 3	4 6	6 9	9 2	1 3	2 6	4 9	6 2	8 5
0.95	9.7572	9.7806	9.8041	9.8276	9.8512	9.8748	9.8985	9.9223	9.9461	9.9700	2 4	4 7	7 1	9 5	1 2	2 6	4 9	6 3	8 7
0.96	9.9939	10.0179	10.0420	10.0661	10.0903	10.1145	10.1388	10.1631	10.1875	10.2120	2 4	4 8	7 3	9 7	1 5	2 0	4 4	6 8	8 4
0.97	10.2365	10.2611	10.2857	10.3104	10.3351	10.3600	10.3848	10.4098	10.4347	10.4598	2 5	5 0	7 4	9 9	1 4	2 9	4 4	6 8	8 4
0.98	10.4849	10.5101	10.5353	10.5606	10.5860	10.6114	10.6369	10.6624	10.6880	10.7136	2 5	5 1	7 6	9 2	1 7	2 3	4 8	6 2	8 4
0.99	10.7394	10.7652	10.7910	10.8169	10.8429	10.8689	10.8950	10.9212	10.9474	10.9737	2 6	5 2	7 8	9 4	1 0	2 6	4 8	6 2	8 5

Table 4: Conversion of 11^y to 10^n in Four Figures

$11^y \rightarrow 10^n$

11^y	10^n												
1	1.0414	16	16.6623	31	32.2832	46	47.9041	61	63.5250	76	79.1458	91	94.7667
2	2.0828	17	17.7037	32	33.3246	47	48.9455	62	64.5663	77	80.1872	92	95.8081
3	3.1242	18	18.7451	33	34.3660	48	49.9868	63	65.6077	78	81.2286	93	96.8495
4	4.1656	19	19.7865	34	35.4074	49	51.0282	64	66.6491	79	82.2700	94	97.8909
5	5.2070	20	20.8279	35	36.4487	50	52.0696	65	67.6905	80	83.3114	95	98.9323
6	6.2484	21	21.8692	36	37.4901	51	53.1110	66	68.7319	81	84.3528	96	99.9737
7	7.2897	22	22.9106	37	38.5315	52	54.1524	67	69.7733	82	85.3942	97	101.0151
8	8.3311	23	23.9520	38	39.5729	53	55.1938	68	70.8147	83	86.4356	98	102.0565
9	9.3725	24	24.9934	39	40.6143	54	56.2352	69	71.8561	84	87.4770	99	103.0979
10	10.4139	25	26.0348	40	41.6557	55	57.2766	70	72.8975	85	88.5184		
11	11.4553	26	27.0762	41	42.6971	56	58.3180	71	73.9389	86	89.5598		
12	12.4967	27	28.1176	42	43.7385	57	59.3594	72	74.9803	87	90.6012		
13	13.5381	28	29.1590	43	44.7799	58	60.4008	73	76.0217	88	91.6426		

14	14.5795	29	30.2004	44	45.8213	59	61.4422	74	77.0631	89	92.6839		
15	15.6209	30	31.2418	45	46.8627	60	62.4836	75	78.1045	90	93.7253		

Table 5: Kifilideen (Power of base 11) of Number in Five Figures

$x \rightarrow Kif\ x$

(x)											Differences									
	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
1	0.00000	0.03975	0.07603	0.10941	0.14032	0.16909	0.19601	0.22129	0.24513	0.26767	2	5	8	1	1	1	2	2	2	
2	0.28906	0.30941	0.32881	0.34735	0.36510	0.38212	0.39848	0.41422	0.42938	0.44402	7	4	1	8	5	2	9	7	2	
3	0.45816	0.47183	0.48507	0.49790	0.51035	0.52244	0.53419	0.54562	0.55674	0.56757	2	4	6	8	0	2	4	7	8	
4	0.57813	0.58843	0.59848	0.60829	0.61788	0.62725	0.63641	0.64538	0.65416	0.66276	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
5	0.67119	0.67845	0.68754	0.69549	0.70328	0.71094	0.71845	0.72583	0.73308	0.74021	7	5	3	0	8	5	3	1	8	
6	0.74722	0.75411	0.76090	0.76757	0.77414	0.78060	0.78697	0.79324	0.79942	0.80551	6	2	9	5	2	8	5	2	7	
7	0.81151	0.81742	0.82326	0.82901	0.83468	0.84028	0.84580	0.85125	0.85664	0.86195	5	1	6	2	7	3	9	5	0	
8	0.86719	0.87238	0.87749	0.88255	0.88754	0.89248	0.89735	0.90218	0.90694	0.91165	4	9	4	9	4	9	4	9	4	
9	0.91631	0.92092	0.92548	0.92999	0.93445	0.93886	0.94323	0.94755	0.95183	0.95606	4	8	3	7	2	6	0	5	9	
10	0.96025	0.96440	0.96851	0.97258	0.97661	0.98060	0.98455	0.98847	0.99235	0.99619	4	8	2	5	9	3	7	2	5	
11	1.00000	1.00377	1.00751	1.01122	1.01490	1.01853	1.02215	1.02573	1.02928	1.03280	3	7	0	4	8	1	5	9	2	
12	1.03629	1.03975	1.04318	1.04658	1.04996	1.05331	1.05663	1.05993	1.06320	1.06645	3	6	0	3	6	0	3	2	7	
13	1.06967	1.07286	1.07603	1.07918	1.08231	1.08541	1.08848	1.09154	1.09457	1.09758	3	6	9	2	5	8	1	5	7	
14	1.10057	1.10354	1.10649	1.10941	1.11232	1.11521	1.11807	1.12092	1.12375	1.12656	2	5	8	1	4	7	0	3	5	
15	1.12934	1.13212	1.13487	1.13760	1.14032	1.14302	1.14570	1.14837	1.15101	1.15364	2	5	8	0	3	6	8	1	4	
16	1.15626	1.15886	1.16144	1.16401	1.16656	1.16909	1.17161	1.17412	1.17661	1.17908	2	5	7	0	2	5	7	0	2	
17	1.18154	1.18399	1.18642	1.18884	1.19124	1.19363	1.19601	1.19837	1.20072	1.20306	2	4	7	9	1	4	6	9	1	
18	1.20538	1.20769	1.20999	1.21227	1.21454	1.21680	1.21905	1.22129	1.22351	1.22573	2	4	6	8	0	1	1	1	1	
19	1.22793	1.23012	1.23229	1.23446	1.23661	1.23876	1.24089	1.24301	1.24513	1.24723	2	4	6	8	0	2	5	7	9	
20	1.24932	1.25140	1.25347	1.25553	1.25758	1.25962	1.26164	1.26366	1.26567	1.26767	0	1	1	2	2	2	3	5	3	
21	1.26966	1.27165	1.27362	1.27558	1.27753	1.27948	1.28141	1.28334	1.28526	1.28716	1	3	5	7	9	1	3	5	7	
22	1.28906	1.29096	1.29284	1.29471	1.29658	1.29844	1.30029	1.30213	1.30396	1.30579	9	7	6	4	3	1	0	0	7	
23	1.30760	1.30941	1.31121	1.31301	1.31479	1.31657	1.31834	1.32011	1.32186	1.32361	1	3	5	7	8	0	1	1	1	
24	1.32535	1.32709	1.32881	1.33053	1.33224	1.33395	1.33565	1.33734	1.33903	1.34070	7	4	1	8	5	2	4	6	8	
25	1.34238	1.34404	1.34570	1.34735	1.34900	1.35063	1.35227	1.35389	1.35551	1.35712	1	3	4	6	8	9	1	3	4	
26	1.35873	1.36033	1.36193	1.36352	1.36510	1.36668	1.36825	1.36981	1.37137	1.37292	1	3	4	6	7	9	1	2	4	
27	1.37447	1.37601	1.37755	1.37908	1.38060	1.38212	1.38364	1.38514	1.38665	1.38815	1	3	4	6	7	9	0	2	3	
28	1.38964	1.39112	1.39261	1.39408	1.39555	1.39702	1.39848	1.39993	1.40139	1.40283	1	2	4	5	7	8	0	1	3	
29	1.40427	1.40571	1.40714	1.40856	1.40998	1.41140	1.41281	1.41422	1.41562	1.41702	1	2	4	5	7	8	9	1	2	
30	1.41841	1.41980	1.42118	1.42256	1.42393	1.42530	1.42667	1.42803	1.42938	1.43074	1	2	4	5	6	8	9	1	2	
31	1.43208	1.43343	1.43477	1.43610	1.43743	1.43876	1.44008	1.44140	1.44271	1.44402	1	2	4	5	6	7	9	0	1	
32	1.44532	1.44663	1.44792	1.44922	1.45050	1.45179	1.45307	1.45435	1.45562	1.45689	1	2	3	5	6	7	9	0	1	
33	1.45816	1.45942	1.46068	1.46193	1.46318	1.46443	1.46567	1.46691	1.46815	1.46938	1	2	3	5	6	7	8	0	1	

34	1.47061	1.47183	1.47305	1.47427	1.47548	1.47669	1.47790	1.47911	1.48031	1.48150	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
35	1.48270	1.48389	1.48507	1.48625	1.48743	1.48861	1.48978	1.49095	1.49212	1.49328	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
36	1.49444	1.49560	1.49675	1.49790	1.49905	1.50020	1.50134	1.50247	1.50361	1.50474	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
37	1.50587	1.50700	1.50812	1.50924	1.51035	1.51147	1.51258	1.51369	1.51479	1.51589	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
38	1.51699	1.51809	1.51918	1.52027	1.52136	1.52244	1.52352	1.52460	1.52568	1.52675	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
39	1.52782	1.52889	1.52996	1.53102	1.53208	1.53314	1.53419	1.53524	1.53629	1.53734	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
40	1.53838	1.53942	1.54046	1.54150	1.54253	1.54356	1.54459	1.54562	1.54664	1.54766	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
41	1.54868	1.54970	1.55071	1.55172	1.55273	1.55373	1.54774	1.55574	1.55674	1.55774	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
42	1.55873	1.55972	1.56071	1.56170	1.56268	1.56366	1.56464	1.56562	1.56660	1.56757	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
43	1.56854	1.56951	1.57048	1.57144	1.57240	1.57336	1.57432	1.57528	1.57623	1.57718	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
44	1.57813	1.57908	1.58002	1.58096	1.58190	1.58284	1.58378	1.58471	1.58564	1.58657	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
45	1.58750	1.58843	1.58935	1.59027	1.59119	1.59211	1.59303	1.59394	1.59485	1.59576	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
46	1.59667	1.59757	1.59848	1.59938	1.60028	1.60118	1.60207	1.60297	1.60386	1.60475	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
47	1.60564	1.60652	1.60741	1.60829	1.60917	1.61005	1.61093	1.61180	1.61267	1.61355	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
48	1.61442	1.61528	1.61615	1.61701	1.61788	1.61874	1.61960	1.62045	1.62131	1.62216	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
49	1.62302	1.62387	1.62471	1.62556	1.62641	1.62725	1.62809	1.62893	1.62977	1.63061	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
50	1.63144	1.63227	1.63311	1.63394	1.63476	1.63559	1.63641	1.63724	1.63806	1.63888	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
51	1.63970	1.64052	1.64133	1.64214	1.64296	1.64377	1.64458	1.64538	1.64619	1.64699	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
52	1.64780	1.64860	1.64940	1.65020	1.65099	1.65179	1.65258	1.65337	1.65416	1.65495	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
53	1.65574	1.65653	1.65731	1.65809	1.65888	1.65966	1.66043	1.66121	1.66199	1.66276	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
54	1.66354	1.66431	1.66508	1.66585	1.66661	1.66738	1.66814	1.66891	1.66967	1.67043	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
55	1.67119	1.67195	1.67270	1.67346	1.67421	1.67496	1.67571	1.67646	1.67721	1.67796	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
56	1.67870	1.67945	1.68019	1.68093	1.68167	1.68241	1.68315	1.68388	1.68462	1.68535	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
57	1.68608	1.68681	1.68754	1.68827	1.68900	1.68973	1.69045	1.69117	1.69190	1.69262	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
58	1.69334	1.69405	1.69477	1.69549	1.69620	1.69692	1.69763	1.69834	1.69905	1.69976	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
59	1.70047	1.70117	1.70188	1.70258	1.70328	1.70398	1.70468	1.70538	1.70608	1.70678	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
60	1.70747	1.70817	1.70886	1.70955	1.71025	1.71094	1.71162	1.71231	1.71300	1.71368	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
61	1.71437	1.71505	1.71573	1.71641	1.71709	1.71777	1.71845	1.71913	1.71980	1.72048	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
62	1.72115	1.72182	1.72249	1.72316	1.72383	1.72450	1.72517	1.72583	1.72650	1.72716	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
63	1.72782	1.72848	1.72914	1.72980	1.73046	1.73112	1.73177	1.73243	1.73308	1.73374	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
64	1.73439	1.73504	1.73569	1.73634	1.73699	1.73763	1.73828	1.73893	1.73957	1.74021	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
65	1.74085	1.74150	1.74214	1.74278	1.74341	1.74405	1.74469	1.74532	1.74596	1.74659	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
66	1.74722	1.74785	1.74848	1.74911	1.74974	1.75037	1.75100	1.75162	1.75225	1.75287	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
67	1.75349	1.75411	1.75474	1.75536	1.75598	1.75659	1.75721	1.75783	1.75844	1.75906	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
68	1.75967	1.76028	1.76090	1.76151	1.76212	1.76273	1.76333	1.76394	1.76455	1.76515	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
69	1.76576	1.76636	1.76697	1.76757	1.76817	1.76877	1.76937	1.76997	1.77057	1.77116	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
70	1.77176	1.77236	1.77295	1.77354	1.77414	1.77473	1.77532	1.77591	1.77650	1.77709	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
71	1.77768	1.77826	1.77885	1.77943	1.78002	1.78060	1.78118	1.78177	1.78235	1.78293	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
72	1.78351	1.78409	1.78467	1.78524	1.78582	1.78639	1.78697	1.78754	1.78812	1.78869	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
73	1.78926	1.78983	1.79040	1.79097	1.79154	1.79211	1.79267	1.79324	1.79381	1.79437	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
74	1.79493	1.79550	1.79606	1.79662	1.79718	1.79774	1.79830	1.79886	1.79942	1.79998	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
75	1.80053	1.80109	1.80164	1.80220	1.80275	1.80330	1.80386	1.80441	1.80496	1.80551	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
76	1.80606	1.80660	1.80715	1.80770	1.80825	1.80879	1.80934	1.80988	1.81042	1.81097	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
77	1.81151	1.81205	0.07603	1.81313	1.81367	1.81421	1.81474	1.81528	1.81582	1.81635	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
78	1.81689	1.81742	0.32881	1.81849	1.81902	1.81955	1.82008	1.82061	1.82114	1.82167	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
79	1.82220	1.82273	0.48507	1.82378	1.82431	1.82483	1.82536	1.82588	1.82640	1.82693	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
80	1.82745	1.82797	0.59848	1.82901	1.82953	1.83005	1.83056	1.83108	1.83160	1.83211	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
81	1.83263	1.83314	0.68754	1.83417	1.83468	1.83519	1.83571	1.83622	1.83673	1.83724	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
82	1.83774	1.83825	0.76090	1.83927	1.83977	1.84028	1.84079	1.84129	1.84179	1.84230	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
83	1.84280	1.84330	0.82326	1.84430	1.84480	1.84530	1.84580	1.84630	1.84680	1.84730	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
84	1.84779	1.84829	0.87749	1.84928	1.84978	1.85027	1.85076	1.85125	1.85175	1.85224	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
85	1.85273	1.85322	0.92548	1.85420	1.85469	1.85518	1.85566	1.85615	1.85664	1.85712	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

86	1.85761	1.85809	0.96851	1.85906	1.85954	1.86002	1.86051	1.86099	1.86147	1.86195		5	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
87	1.86243	1.86291	1.00751	1.86386	1.86434	1.86482	1.86529	1.86577	1.86625	1.86672		5	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
88	1.86719	1.86767	1.04318	1.86861	1.86909	1.86956	1.87003	1.87050	1.87097	1.87144		5	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
89	1.87191	1.87238	1.07603	1.87331	1.87378	1.87424	1.87471	1.87517	1.87564	1.87610		5	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
90	1.87657	1.87703	1.10649	1.87795	1.87842	1.87888	1.87934	1.87980	1.88026	1.88072		5	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
91	1.88117	1.88163	1.13487	1.88255	1.88300	1.88346	1.88392	1.88370	1.88482	1.88528		5	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
92	1.88573	1.88619	1.16144	1.88709	1.88754	1.88799	1.88844	1.88889	1.88934	1.88979		5	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
93	1.89024	1.89069	1.18642	1.89158	1.89203	1.89248	1.89292	1.89337	1.89381	1.89426		5	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
94	1.89470	1.89514	1.20999	1.89603	1.89647	1.89691	1.89735	1.89780	1.89824	1.89867		4	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
95	1.89911	1.89955	1.23229	1.90043	1.90087	1.90130	1.90174	1.90218	1.90261	1.90305		4	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
96	1.90348	1.90392	1.25347	1.90478	1.90522	1.90565	1.90608	1.90651	1.90694	1.90737		4	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
97	1.90780	1.90823	1.27362	1.90909	1.90952	1.90995	1.91037	1.91080	1.91123	1.91165		4	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
98	1.91208	1.91251	1.29284	1.91335	1.91378	1.91420	1.91463	1.91505	1.91547	1.91589		4	9	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
99	1.91631	1.91673	1.31121	1.91758	1.91800	1.91841	1.91883	1.91925	1.91967	1.92009		4	8	1	1	2	2	3	3	4

Table 6: Kifilideen (Power of base 11) of 10^n in Five Figures

$Kif(10^n)$

10^n	11^y	10^n	11^y	10^n	11^y	10^n	11^y	10^n	11^y
10^n	$Kif(10^n)$	10^n	$Kif(10^n)$	10^n	$Kif(10^n)$	10^n	$Kif(10^n)$	10^n	$Kif(10^n)$
n = 1	y = 0.96025	n = 21	y = 20.16530	n = 41	y = 39.37036	n = 61	y = 58.57541	n = 81	y = 77.78046
2	1.92051	22	21.12556	42	40.33061	62	59.53566	82	78.74071
3	2.88076	23	22.08581	43	41.29086	63	60.49591	83	79.70096
4	3.84101	24	23.04606	44	42.25111	64	61.45616	84	80.66122
5	4.80126	25	24.00631	45	43.21137	65	62.41642	85	81.62147
6	5.76152	26	24.96657	46	44.17162	66	63.37667	86	82.58172
7	6.72177	27	25.92682	47	45.13187	67	64.33692	87	83.54197
8	7.68202	28	26.88707	48	46.09212	68	65.29717	88	84.50222
9	8.64227	29	27.84732	49	47.05238	69	66.25743	89	85.46248
10	9.60253	30	28.80758	50	48.01263	70	67.21768	90	86.42273
11	10.56278	31	29.76783	51	48.97288	71	68.17793	91	87.38298
12	11.52303	32	30.72808	52	49.93313	72	69.13818	92	88.34323
13	12.48328	33	31.68833	53	50.89339	73	70.09844	93	89.30349
14	13.44354	34	32.64859	54	51.85364	74	71.05869	94	90.26374
15	14.40379	35	33.60884	55	52.81389	75	72.01894	95	91.22399
16	15.36404	36	34.56909	56	53.77414	76	72.97920	96	92.18425
17	16.32429	37	35.52935	57	54.73440	77	73.93945	97	93.14450
18	17.28455	38	36.48960	58	55.69465	78	74.89970	98	94.10475
19	18.24480	39	37.44985	59	56.65490	79	75.85995	99	95.06500
20	19.20505	40	38.41010	60	57.61515	80	76.82021		

Table 7: AntiKifilideen (AntiPower of base 11) of Number in Five Figures

$x \rightarrow$ AntiKif x

(x)	Difference									
	0	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.007	0.008	0.009
0.00	1.00000	1.00240	1.00481	1.00722	1.00964	1.01206	1.01449	1.01693	1.01937	1.02182
0.01	1.02427	1.02673	1.02919	1.03166	1.03414	1.03662	1.03911	1.04161	1.04411	1.04661
0.02	1.04913	1.05165	1.05417	1.05670	1.05924	1.06178	1.06433	1.06688	1.06945	1.07201
0.03	1.07459	1.07717	1.07975	1.08235	1.08494	1.08755	1.09016	1.09278	1.09540	1.09803
0.04	1.10067	1.10331	1.10596	1.10861	1.11127	1.11394	1.11662	1.11930	1.12198	1.12468
0.05	1.12738	1.13008	1.13280	1.13552	1.13824	1.14098	1.14372	1.14646	1.14921	1.15197
0.06	1.15474	1.15751	1.16029	1.16308	1.16587	1.16867	1.17147	1.17428	1.17710	1.17993
0.07	1.18276	1.18560	1.18845	1.19130	1.19416	1.19703	1.19990	1.20278	1.20567	1.20857
0.08	1.21147	1.21437	1.21729	1.22021	1.22314	1.22608	1.22902	1.23197	1.23493	1.23790
0.09	1.24087	1.24385	1.24683	1.24983	1.25283	1.25583	1.25885	1.26187	1.26490	1.26794
0.10	1.27098	1.27493	1.27709	1.28016	1.28323	1.28631	1.28940	1.29250	1.29560	1.29871
0.11	1.30183	1.30495	1.30809	1.31123	1.31437	1.31753	1.32069	1.32386	1.32704	1.33023
0.12	1.33342	1.33662	1.33983	1.34305	1.34627	1.34950	1.35274	1.35599	1.35925	1.36251
0.13	1.36578	1.36906	1.37235	1.37564	1.37894	1.38225	1.38557	1.38890	1.39223	1.39558

0.14	1.39893	1.40229	1.40565	1.40903	1.41241	1.41580	1.41920	1.42261	1.42602	1.42945	3	6	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
											4	8	2	3	7	0	3	7	0	6
0.15	1.43288	1.43632	1.43977	1.44322	1.44669	1.45016	1.45364	1.45713	1.46063	1.46414	3	6	0	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
											5	9	4	9	4	9	3	4	7	1
0.16	1.46765	1.47117	1.47471	1.47825	1.48180	1.48535	1.48892	1.49249	1.49608	1.49967	3	7	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
											6	1	7	2	8	4	9	5	1	2
0.17	1.50327	1.50688	1.51050	1.51412	1.51776	1.52140	1.52505	1.52871	1.53239	1.53606	3	7	0	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
											6	3	9	6	2	9	5	9	2	2
0.18	1.53975	1.54345	1.54715	1.55087	1.55459	1.55832	1.56206	1.56581	1.56957	1.57334	3	7	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
											7	5	2	9	7	4	1	9	6	6
0.19	1.57712	1.58091	1.58470	1.58851	1.59232	1.59614	1.59997	1.60382	1.60767	1.61153	3	7	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
											8	6	5	3	1	0	8	6	4	4
0.20	1.61539	1.61927	1.62316	1.62706	1.63096	1.63488	1.63880	1.64274	1.64668	1.65064	3	7	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
											9	8	8	7	6	5	4	4	3	5
0.21	1.65460	1.65857	1.66255	1.66654	1.67054	1.67456	1.67858	1.68261	1.68664	1.69069	4	8	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3
											0	0	0	6	0	4	8	2	6	6
0.22	1.69475	1.69882	1.70290	1.70699	1.71109	1.71519	1.71931	1.72344	1.72758	1.73172	4	8	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3
											1	2	3	4	6	7	8	9	0	7
0.23	1.73588	1.74005	1.74423	1.74841	1.75261	1.75682	1.76104	1.76527	1.76950	1.77375	4	8	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3
											2	4	6	8	1	5	9	3	7	7
0.24	1.77801	1.78228	1.78656	1.79085	1.79515	1.79946	1.80378	1.80811	1.81245	1.81680	4	8	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3
											3	6	9	2	6	9	2	5	8	8
0.25	1.82116	1.82553	1.82992	1.83431	1.83871	1.84313	1.84755	1.85199	1.85643	1.86089	4	8	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	3
											4	8	2	7	2	6	0	5	9	9
0.26	1.86536	1.86984	1.87432	1.87882	1.88334	1.88786	1.89239	1.89693	1.90149	1.90605	4	9	3	3	2	2	2	2	3	3
											5	0	6	1	6	1	7	2	7	4
0.27	1.91063	1.91521	1.91981	1.92442	1.92904	1.93367	1.93832	1.94297	1.94763	1.95231	4	9	3	3	2	2	2	2	3	3
											6	3	9	5	2	8	4	1	7	1
0.28	1.95700	1.96169	1.96640	1.97112	1.97586	1.98060	1.98536	1.99012	1.99490	1.99969	4	9	4	4	3	3	3	3	4	4
											7	5	2	0	7	5	2	0	7	2
0.29	2.00449	2.00930	2.01413	2.01896	2.02381	2.02867	2.03354	2.03842	2.04331	2.04822	4	9	4	4	3	2	2	2	3	3
											9	7	6	4	3	2	0	9	8	4
0.30	2.05314	2.05807	2.06301	2.06796	2.07292	2.07790	2.08289	2.08789	2.09290	2.09793	5	0	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
											0	0	9	9	9	9	9	9	8	8
0.31	2.10296	2.10801	2.11307	2.11815	2.12323	2.12833	2.13344	2.13856	2.14369	2.14884	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	5
											1	2	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	9
0.32	2.15400	2.15917	2.16435	2.16955	2.17476	2.17998	2.18521	2.19046	2.19572	2.20099	5	0	5	0	6	1	6	1	7	7
											2	4	7	9	1	3	6	8	0	0
0.33	2.20627	2.21157	2.21688	2.22220	2.22754	2.23289	2.23825	2.24362	2.24901	2.25441	5	0	6	1	6	2	7	2	8	8
											3	7	0	4	8	1	5	8	2	2
0.34	2.25982	2.26524	2.27068	2.27613	2.28160	2.28708	2.29257	2.29807	2.30359	2.30912	5	1	6	1	7	2	8	3	9	9
											5	0	4	9	4	9	4	9	4	4
0.35	2.31466	2.32022	2.32579	2.33137	2.33697	2.34258	2.34820	2.35384	2.35949	2.36516	5	1	6	2	8	3	9	4	0	5
											6	2	8	5	1	7	3	9	6	6
0.36	2.37084	2.37653	2.38223	2.38795	2.39368	2.39943	2.40519	2.41097	2.41675	2.42256	5	1	7	3	8	4	0	6	1	1
											7	5	2	0	8	5	3	0	8	8
0.37	2.42837	2.43420	2.44005	2.44590	2.45178	2.45766	2.46356	2.46948	2.47541	2.48135	5	1	7	3	8	5	1	7	3	3
											9	8	7	6	4	3	2	1	0	4
0.38	2.48731	2.49328	2.49926	2.50526	2.51128	2.51731	2.52335	2.52941	2.53548	2.54157	6	2	8	4	0	6	2	8	4	5
											0	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	3	3
0.39	2.54767	2.55379	2.55992	2.56606	2.57222	2.57840	2.58459	2.59079	2.59701	2.60325	6	2	8	4	0	7	3	9	5	5
											2	4	5	7	9	1	3	5	6	6
0.40	2.60950	2.61576	2.62204	2.62834	2.63465	2.64097	2.64731	2.65367	2.66004	2.66643	6	2	9	5	1	8	4	0	7	7
											3	7	0	3	6	0	3	7	0	0
0.41	2.67283	2.67924	2.68568	2.69212	2.69859	2.70507	2.71156	2.71807	2.72460	2.73114	6	3	9	5	2	8	5	1	8	8
											5	0	4	9	4	9	4	9	4	4
0.42	2.73769	2.74427	2.75086	2.75746	2.76408	2.77072	2.77737	2.78403	2.79072	2.79742	6	3	9	6	3	9	6	3	9	9
											6	3	9	6	2	8	5	1	8	8
0.43	2.80413	2.81087	2.81761	2.82438	2.83116	2.83796	2.84477	2.85160	2.85845	2.86531	6	3	0	7	4	0	7	4	1	1
											8	6	4	2	0	8	6	4	2	2
0.44	2.87219	2.87908	2.88599	2.89292	2.89987	2.90683	2.91381	2.92080	2.92782	2.93485	7	3	0	7	4	1	8	5	2	2
											0	9	9	9	8	8	8	8	7	7
0.45	2.94189	2.94895	2.95603	2.96313	2.97025	2.97738	2.98452	2.99169	2.99887	3.00607	7	4	1	8	5	2	0	7	4	4

0.50	3.31662	3.32459	3.33257	3.34057	3.34859	3.35663	3.36469	3.37277	3.38086	3.38898	8	2	2	3	4	4	5	6	7
											0	6	4	2	2	8	6	4	2
											1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
0.51	3.39712	3.40527	3.41345	3.42164	3.42986	3.43809	3.44634	3.45462	3.46291	3.47123	8	6	4	3	1	8	7	5	4
											2	5	7	0	2	4	7	9	2
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
0.52	3.47956	3.48791	3.49629	3.50468	3.51309	3.52153	3.52998	3.53846	3.54695	3.55547	8	6	5	3	2	0	9	7	6
											4	9	3	8	2	6	1	5	0
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
0.53	3.56400	3.57256	3.58114	3.58973	3.59835	3.60699	3.61565	3.62433	3.63303	3.64175	8	7	5	4	3	1	0	9	7
											6	3	9	6	2	9	5	2	8
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
0.54	3.65050	3.65926	3.66805	3.67685	3.68568	3.69453	3.70340	3.71229	3.72120	3.73014	8	7	6	4	3	1	0	9	7
											8	7	6	4	3	1	0	9	7
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
0.55	3.73909	3.74807	3.75707	3.76609	3.77513	3.78419	3.79328	3.80238	3.81151	3.82066	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
											1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
0.56	3.82983	3.83903	3.84824	3.85748	3.86674	3.87603	3.88533	3.89466	3.90401	3.91338	9	8	7	7	6	5	4	3	2
											3	6	9	2	4	7	0	3	6
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
0.57	3.92278	3.93220	3.94164	3.95110	3.96059	3.97009	3.97963	3.98918	3.99876	4.00836	9	9	8	8	7	7	6	5	4
											5	0	5	1	6	1	6	1	7
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
0.58	4.01798	4.02763	4.03730	4.04699	4.05670	4.06644	4.07621	4.08599	4.09580	4.10563	9	9	9	9	8	8	8	7	6
											7	5	2	0	7	5	2	0	7
											1	2	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
0.59	4.11549	4.12537	4.13528	4.14520	4.15516	4.16513	4.17513	4.18515	4.19520	4.20527	0	0	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
											0	0	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.60	4.21537	4.22549	4.23563	4.24580	4.25600	4.26621	4.27646	4.28672	4.29701	4.30733	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	2
											2	4	7	9	1	4	6	8	1
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.61	4.31767	4.32804	4.33843	4.34884	4.35928	4.36975	4.38024	4.39076	4.40130	4.41186	0	0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
											5	9	4	9	4	8	3	8	3
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.62	4.42246	4.43307	4.44372	4.45438	4.46508	4.47580	4.48654	4.49731	4.50811	4.51893	0	1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6
											7	4	2	9	6	4	1	8	6
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.63	4.52978	4.54066	4.55156	4.56249	4.57344	4.58442	4.59543	4.60646	4.61752	4.62860	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8
											0	0	0	9	9	9	9	9	9
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.64	4.63972	4.65085	4.66202	4.67321	4.68443	4.69568	4.70695	4.71825	4.72958	4.74093	1	2	3	5	6	7	8	9	0
											2	5	8	0	3	5	8	1	3
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.65	4.75232	4.76372	4.77516	4.78663	4.79812	4.80964	4.82118	4.83276	4.84436	4.85599	1	3	4	6	7	9	0	2	3
											5	0	6	1	6	2	7	2	8
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.66	4.86765	4.87933	4.89105	4.90279	4.91456	4.92636	4.93819	4.95004	4.96193	4.97384	1	3	5	7	9	0	2	4	6
											8	6	4	2	0	8	7	5	3
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.67	4.98578	4.99775	5.00975	5.02178	5.03383	5.04592	5.05803	5.07017	5.08235	5.09455	2	4	6	8	0	2	4	6	8
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
											1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.68	5.10678	5.11904	5.13133	5.14365	5.15600	5.16837	5.18078	5.19322	5.20569	5.21819	2	4	7	9	1	4	6	9	1
											4	8	1	5	9	3	7	1	5
											1	2	3	5	6	7	8	0	1
0.69	5.23071	5.24327	5.25586	5.26848	5.28113	5.29380	5.30651	5.31925	5.33202	5.34482	2	5	8	0	3	6	8	1	4
											7	4	1	7	4	1	8	5	2
											1	2	3	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.70	5.35766	5.37052	5.38341	5.39634	5.40929	5.42228	5.43530	5.44835	5.46143	5.47454	3	6	9	2	5	8	1	4	7
											0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
											1	2	3	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.71	5.48768	5.50086	5.51406	5.52730	5.54057	5.55387	5.56720	5.58057	5.59397	5.60740	3	6	9	3	6	9	3	6	9
											3	6	9	2	5	9	2	5	8
											1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.72	5.62086	5.63435	5.64788	5.66144	5.67503	5.68866	5.70231	5.71600	5.72973	5.74348	4	7	1	5	9	3	7	1	5
											6	3	9	5	2	8	5	1	8
											1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.73	5.75727	5.77109	5.78485	5.79864	5.81276	5.82671	5.84070	5.85472	5.86878	5.88287	4	7	1	5	9	3	7	1	5
											0	9	9	8	8	8	8	8	7
											1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.74	5.89699	5.91115	5.92534	5.93957	5.95383	5.96812	5.98245	5.99681	6.01121	6.02564	4	8	2	7	1	5	0	4	8
											3	6	9	2	5	8	1	5	8
											1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.75	6.04011	6.05461	6.06914	6.08371	6.09832	6.11296	6.12763	6.14235	6.15709	6.17187	4	9	3	8	3	7	2	7	1
											6	3	9	6	2	9	6	2	9
											1	3	4	6	7	8	9	0	1
0.76	6.18669	6.20154	6.21643	6.23136	6.24632	6.26131	6.27634	6.29141	6.30652	6.32166	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	5
											0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
											1	3	4	6	7	8	9	0	1
0.77	6.33683	6.35205	6.36730	6.38258	6.39791	6.41327	6.42866	6.44410	6.45957	6.47508	5	0	6	1	6	2	7	3	8
											4	7	1	5	8	2	6	0	4
											1	3	4	6	7	8	9	0	1
0.78	6.49062	6.50620	6.52182	6.53748	6.55318	6.56891	6.58468	6.60049	6.61633	6.63222	5	1	7	3	8	4	0	6	1
											7	5	2	0	7	5	2	0	8
											1	3	4	6	7	8	9	0	1
0.79	6.64814	6.66410	6.68010	6.69614	6.71221	6.72833	6.74448	6.76067	6.77690	6.79317	6	2	8	4	0	6	2	9	5
											1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
											1	3	4	6	7	8	9	0	1
0.80	6.80948	6.82583	6.84222	6.85865	6.87511	6.89162	6.90816	6.92475	6.94137	6.95804	6	3	9	6	2	9	1	1	1
											5	0	5	1	6	1	1	3	4

Conclusion

This paper presents the four and five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables for the computation of mathematical problem. The four and five figures are both reliable to work with. However there is tradeoff between easy computation (as related to four figure table) and more accuracy (as related to five figure table) in their utilization.

Availability of Data and Materials

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

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Competing Interests

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References

Osanyinpeju, K.L.: Development of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) and Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) Tables. 1st International Conference on Engineering and Environmental Sciences (ICEES), Osun State University, Theme: Advancing Technology and Environment Burdens (Challenges and Sustainable Solution) 5th- 7th November 2019 pp 957 – 968 (2019)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5794620>

Osanyinpeju, K.L.;Aderinlewo, A.A.;Dairo, O.U.;Adetunji, O.R.; Ajesegiri, E.S.A.: Development, Conversion and Application of Osanyinpeju (Power of Base 2) and Antiosanyinpeju (Antipower of Base 2) with Lekan (Power of Base 5) and Antilekan (Antipower of Base 5) Tables.Ist International Conference on Engineering and Environmental Science, Osun State University. November 5 – 7, 2019 Pp 969 – 982 (2019).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5818003>

Osanyinpeju, K.L.: Development of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11), Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) and Other Tables.Eliva Press SRL Publisher, MD-2060, bd. Cuza-Voda, ¼, of. 21 Chisinau, Republica Moldova, Europe 136 pp, (2020).
<https://www.amazon.com/Development-Kifilideen-Antikifilideen-Antipower-Tables/dp/B0884BP9TS>